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Needs, Competencies, and Problems of Retirees: Inputs to an Enhanced Retirement Program

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Abstract

This study determined the needs, competencies, and problems of retirees as a basis for an enhanced retirement program. A survey questionnaire was used to gather data from 250 respondents, retirees, in the years 2021-2025. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, and means). To determine whether there are significant differences in needs, competencies, and the extent of problems met between government and non-government retirees, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and t-tests were used. Results showed that a retiree opts to retire early at age 60 to continue working in a different capacity. Financial security remains the central issue for retirees in the remaining years because of the loss of earning power after retirement and the associated medical expenses. Retirees constitute a large pool of talent that society can still benefit from. There are no significant differences between the needs, competencies, and problems of Government and Non-Government retirees. Based on the results of this study, a more responsive Program Framework tailored to Filipino Retirees, coined "*Masigla't Makabuluhang Pagreretiro*," has been proposed.

Keywords: Enhanced Retirement Program, Competencies, Government and Non-Government Retirees, Needs, Problems, *Masigla't Makabuluhang Pagreretiro*